

THE PLACE OF THE LANDSCAPE GENRE IN THE FINE ARTS AND SIGNIFICANCE

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Abstract. *In this article, the feeling towards nature is interpreted through the landscape genre of fine art. Emphasis is placed on the perception of existence through works of visual art.*

Key words: *education, learners, cooperation, pedagogy, master-disciple tradition, landscape, genre.*

МЕСТО ЖАНРА ПЕЙЗАЖА В ИЗОБРАЗИТЕЛЬНОМ ИСКУССТВЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье чувство к природе интерпретируется через пейзажный жанр изобразительного искусства. Акцент делается на восприятии бытия через произведения изобразительного искусства.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, учащиеся, сотрудничество, педагогика, традиция мастер-ученик, пейзаж, жанр.*

You know, art leads a person to goodness, sometimes when we analyze the works of art, the rules and methods of composition gradually lose their essence, and new rules of composition begin to appear. When creating a work of art, artists naturally and consciously follow the laws of composition. Every social society sets new modern tasks before art.

Currently, we divide the theoretical foundations of composition into two groups we learn separately.

1. Laws of composition.
2. Rules and methods of composition.

"Composition method (ways). One of the main methods of composition is to express the rhythm, determine the center of the subject of the composition, its symmetrical or asymmetrical position, and place the main device of the mass in the background. The presence of rhythm in life and art is a good sign for the artist, it is a means of repeating one element in intervals. In perceiving the idea of the work, the structure of the composition, the rhythm plays the role of an aesthetic imagery, and the contrast relies on the laws of color and tone. Any artist learns the heritage and experiences of past masters of painting, as well as the method of painting and composition, which has a deep impact on the viewer.¹

In practice, there are necessary elements of composition. The law of unity, the law of analogy, the law of contrast, the means of content and the subordination of the idea are considered the main laws of composition.

The signs of this law are E. Because of the law of the first sign of unity in composition, which is fully and deeply analyzed in Kibrick's book, the work of art appears as an indivisible whole. In the whole of the composition, the elements of the composition are represented by shape,

¹ file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/manzara-zhanrini-tasviriy-sanatdagi-rni-va-tarbiyaviy-a-amiyati.pdf

volume, "palatno", intermediate character, copy, gesture. As an example, I. Repin's painting "Krestnoy Khod v Kurskoy Gubernii" appears at first glance in the form of a whole "pyatno". The image of the crowd in the composition is located diagonally and connects the four corners of the picture. In the end, although a large number of depraved communities are depicted, each person's character, copy, negative and positive images, class antagonisms, Russian society in general is expressed. The law of truth is basically represented by three symbols. The first sign is the uniqueness of the situation of the event happening in the work of art. A. Savrasov's "Black crows came flying", I. Levita's "Golden Autumn", A. In Kuindzhi's "Kaynzorda" and A. Ro'lov's "The air is in the vastness" scenes, content, sophistication, as well as a unique image of Russian nature are depicted. The second sign of the law of typification describes the subject of the event, the state of the action and the time.

Yu. In "New Moscow", "Wedding on the Streets of Tomorrow", Pimenev showed the modern city life in motion, which is changing before our eyes. In the direction of the wedding ceremony, it is the state of the people who are taking a step towards the future life. The third sign of the law of typification is novelty.

Realistic art does not accurately express the truth, but the artist glorifies feelings, aesthetic beauty, and imagination. Aesthetic qualities in an artistic image, novelties in the solution of composition are discovered by the artist. Aesthetic discoveries in the immortal works of Michelangelo, Titian, Rembrant, A. Deineka, A. In the works of Plastov, K. Yuon, we can see the concept of novelty in the theme of compositional structure from artistic means.

"Novizna" - the stream of news we see. We see it in Kuindzhi's "Birches", V. Polenov's "Yard in Moscow". Landscape art has the power to positively affect a person by reflecting the beauty of the outside world. Therefore, the artist expresses his aesthetic attitude towards nature, understanding the most delicate, typical situations, color harmonies of the natural world. In the landscape work, he sings his personality, intelligence, and inner feelings through images and creates an image of nature. As an example, I. Levitan's "Vladimirka", "Over Eternal Silence", I. Shishkin, "Forest Distances", V. Meshkov's "Thoughts about the Urals" can be cited. ²

The works of the landscape genre in the fine arts form the qualities of nature and beauty in a person. Artists write etudes and sketches directly referring to the landscape in works on historical and domestic topics. In this case, the landscape serves as an additional background in the picture.

V. Vasnetsov's "Alyonushka" is an example of this. Natural beauty, innovative changes typical of the time K. Yuon, G. Artists such as Nissky also depicted and demonstrated in their works. U. U. Tansikboev "Issik kol", "Motherland", "Qayraqkum reservoir", N. Karakhan "Nanay Yoli", "Spring in Sijjak", R. Timurov created a collection of architectural landscapes of Samarkand. G. Abdurakhmanov, F. Tokhirov in 70-80 years. Artists such as R. Choriev, K. Bogadukhov, M. Esin, Pudovkin created effectively in the landscape genre.

Currently, many sought-after talented artists, A. Nuritdinov, O. Qazokov, Z. Islamshikov, A. Mominov, A. People like Mirsoatov created charming landscapes praising the beautiful nature of independent Uzbekistan.

² file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/manzara-zhanrini-tasviriy-sanatdagi-rni-va-tarbiyaviy-a-amiyati.pdf

There are several types of landscape. City (Architecture), rural (mountain) landscape, industrial (factory, factory, construction), historical, romantic, lyrical, panoramic (view) landscapes are among them. To create a composition in this genre, it is necessary to have excellent knowledge in the fields of pencil drawing and painting.

Line color sketches drawn from nature can be the main subject in creating a landscape composition. If we want to describe the composition of the rural landscape, first of all, we should carefully observe the characteristic places of sunny, cloudy days, noon, and evening in nature.

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